

OPEN LETTER

REVISED **The ENDOMIX project: an interdisciplinary approach to understanding how real-life chemical mixtures target the immune system to trigger disease**

[version 2; peer review: 3 approved with reservations]

Ana Claudia Zenclussen ⁷

¹Department of Environmental Immunology, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Leipzig, Saxony, 04318, Germany

²German Center for Child and Adolescent Health (DZKJ), partner site Leipzig/Dresden, Leipzig, Germany

³European Institute for Biomedical Imaging Research (EIBIR), Vienna, Austria

⁴German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), Dept. Food Safety, Berlin, 10589, Germany

⁵RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, South Moravian Region, Czech Republic

⁶Department of Cell Toxicology, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Leipzig, Saxony, 04318, Germany

⁷Univ Rennes, Inserm, EHESP, Institut de Recherche en Santé, Environnement et Travail - UMR_S 1085, Rennes, France

⁸Department of Pediatrics, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

⁹Generation R Study Group, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

¹⁰Department of Neonatal and Intensive Care, Division of Neonatology, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center, Rotterdam, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

¹¹Institute for Global Health, ISGlobal, Barcelona, Spain

¹²Fraunhofer Institute for Biomedical Engineering IBMT, Sulzbach, Germany

¹³Epidemiology and Environmental Health Joint Research Unit, FISABIO-Universitat Jaume I-Universitat de València, Valencia, Spain

¹⁴Spanish Consortium for Research on Epidemiology and Public Health (CIBERESP), Madrid, Spain

¹⁵Department of Nursing, Faculty of Nursing and Chiropody, University of Valencia, Valencia, Spain

¹⁶University Grenoble Alpes, Inserm U-1209, CNRS-UMR-5309, Environmental Epidemiology Applied to Development and Respiratory Health Team, Institute for Advanced Biosciences, Grenoble, France

¹⁷Institute for Risk Assessment Sciences, Utrecht University, Utrecht, The Netherlands

¹⁸MRC Centre for Environment and Health, School of Public Health, Imperial College London, London, UK

¹⁹Department of Molecular Toxicology, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Leipzig, Saxony, 04318, Germany

²⁰Department of Ecotoxicology, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Leipzig, Saxony, 04318, Germany

V2 First published: 19 Dec 2024, 4:271
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19088.1>

Latest published: 21 Nov 2025, 4:271
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19088.2>

Abstract

The true impact of endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) on human health is far from being understood. Humans are exposed to mixtures of chemicals throughout their lives, yet regulations and most studies focus on individual chemicals. ENDOMIX takes a novel approach to identifying associations and causality between EDCs and adverse health outcomes by focusing on exposure to mixtures of EDCs over the life course, including windows of susceptibility, using human biomonitoring data from several European cohorts. We will model and measure how real-life EDC mixtures act together and target the immune system to initiate, trigger or maintain disease. Health effects will be investigated using pioneering methodologies ranging from high-throughput *in vitro* bioassays, sophisticated organoid and co-culture systems, to *in vivo* models. In combination, they will provide valuable information on mechanistic pathways and transgenerational effects of EDC exposure. We aim to identify biomarkers and patterns of chemical exposures that are easy to measure, available for large cohorts and indicative for adverse health outcomes. We will use *in vitro*, *in silico* and *in vivo* data to strengthen causal inference using a weight-of-evidence approach. Moreover, using novel text mining methods, we will create knowledge graphs to capture and summarize the complexity of biomechanistic information, which aids rapid risk assessments and the creation of network models. The knowledge generated by ENDOMIX will provide an evidence base for policy-making and also reach people of all ages to raise awareness of the risks of EDC exposure and encourage health-promoting behaviors.

Keywords

endocrine disrupting chemicals, EDC exposure, chemical mixtures, immune system, long-term health effects, interdisciplinary approach, science to policy translation

This article is included in the [Horizon Europe gateway](#).

Open Peer Review

Approval Status **???**

	1	2	3
version 2 (revision) 21 Nov 2025			
version 1 19 Dec 2024	? view	? view	? view

1. **Lyuba Varticovski** , National Institutes of Health, Maryland, USA
2. **Jacques Robert** , University of Rochester Medical Center, Rochester, USA
3. **Josef Köhrle** , Charité-Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Berlin, Germany

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

H2020

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020 gateway](#).

Corresponding author: Ana Claudia Zenclussen (ana.zenclussen@ufz.de)

Author roles: **Zenclussen AC:** Conceptualization, Funding Acquisition, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Belmar Erilkin V:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Böhmert L:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Borilova Linhartova P:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Braeuning A:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Braun G:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Chevrier C:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Duijts L:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Escher BI:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Felix J:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Gómez-Olarte S:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Guxens M:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Herberth G:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Hilscherova K:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Klanova J:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Kohl Y:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Krischak K:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Lagadic-Gossmann D:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Langouët S:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Llop S:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Lopez-Espinosa MJ:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Maitre L:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Martin-Chouly C:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Meyer N:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Ouidir M:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Pham TAM:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Philippat C:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Pieters R:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Pinel-Marie ML:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Podechard N:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Polte T:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Price E:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Robinson O:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Schubert K:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Schumacher A:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Stojanovska V:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Tal T:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Vineis P:** Writing – Review & Editing; **van Vorstenbosch R:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Vermeulen R:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Warembourg C:** Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. (Understanding how endocrine disruptors and chemical mixtures of concern target the immune system to trigger or perpetuate disease [ENDOMIX, GA No 101136566]). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 857560 (CETOCOEN Excellence). We acknowledge support from the grant CEX2023-0001290-S funded by MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033, and support from the Generalitat de Catalunya through the CERCA Program. Authors thank RECETOX RI (No LM2023069) and BBMRI.cz (No LM2023033) financed by the Czech MEYS for supportive background.

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2025 Zenclussen AC *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Zenclussen AC, Belmar Erilkin V, Böhmert L *et al.* **The ENDOMIX project: an interdisciplinary approach to understanding how real-life chemical mixtures target the immune system to trigger disease [version 2; peer review: 3 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2025, 4:271 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openresearch.19088.2>

First published: 19 Dec 2024, 4:271 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openresearch.19088.1>

REVISED Amendments from Version 1

In response to the reviewers' comments, we have revised the manuscript to clarify and improve several aspects related to the ENDOMIX conception and objectives.

We have added a paragraph to the ENDOMIX conception section that provides a more detailed methodological explanation of the tiered approach used to investigate the effects of chemicals and their mixtures across models of increasing physiological complexity, ranging from cell-based systems to *in vivo* models. We have also elaborated further on the triangulation strategy employed within ENDOMIX to generate a coherent, causality-oriented framework that connects environmental exposure to immune dysregulation and disease risk.

In the Objective 3 section, we have also expanded the description of the approaches applied within ENDOMIX to illustrate how EDCs may alter immune responses against pathogens.

Any further responses from the reviewers can be found at the end of the article

Introduction

Endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are natural or synthetic chemicals that interfere with the normal functioning of the endocrine system in humans and animals. However, the impact of EDCs in general and man-made chemicals in particular on human health is not so well-understood. They are ubiquitous and have been implicated in the increase in the prevalence of common non-communicable diseases (NCDs) over the last decade¹. Man-made EDC chemicals, from here on referred to as EDCs, can be found not only in the environment (water, soil, air), but also in consumer products (plastics, food packaging, electronics and food packaging), in personal care products (e.g., sunscreen, cosmetics), as well as in food and drinking water². Efforts to minimize exposure to harmful EDCs include regulations on their use in consumer products, bans on certain chemicals, and public education campaigns to raise awareness of their potential adverse health risks. Many of these approaches rely on results obtained from scenarios on exposure to single chemicals or at best to a family of chemicals. In reality, however, we are exposed to multiple EDCs simultaneously throughout our lives. Not only do some EDCs accumulate in the environment and enrich in certain tissues³, but their mixtures will lead to additive, and in rare cases, synergistic or antagonistic effects⁴.

Deviations from normal healthy state or development do cause individual suffering and impose enormous costs on health care systems⁵. Although ample evidence of the adverse effects of EDC exposure in wildlife and animals was already reported by the International Program on Chemical Safety in 2002 and has been complemented by a large number of epidemiological studies over the past decades, significant gaps still remain in our understanding of the health effects and mechanisms of EDC in the human population^{3,6-8}. The so-called immunotoxicology lists among the less explored topics. Indeed, the effects of EDCs on the immune system have been poorly investigated. However, dysregulated immune pathways may underlie and are important drivers of common human diseases.

The fact that EDCs may affect the immune system and cause abnormalities relevant to disease is poorly addressed⁵. Despite growing evidence feeding to this emergent field of research, more research is needed to fully understand the breadth of EDCs' impact on the immune system, especially concerning long-term health effects and the combined impact of multiple disruptors to which we are exposed chronically. Additionally, understanding individual and group susceptibility needs to be considered.

In this article we present the concept and objectives of the ENDOMIX project to address the above-mentioned challenges and needs.

ENDOMIX conception

The vision and aim of ENDOMIX is to thoroughly clarify and understand the overall immunotoxic or immunomodulatory impact of EDC mixtures and underlying mechanisms leading to adverse health outcomes. ENDOMIX is a cutting-edge research initiative that aims to uncover the true impact of EDCs on human health by bridging existing knowledge gaps between science and policy. It was born out of the need to synthesize available information from different approaches and sources, and the urgent demands of society to protect individual health by reducing exposure to and minimizing chemical risks. The project takes an interdisciplinary approach, covering the full chain from population-based studies to mechanistic understanding of EDC effects at the cellular and target organ level, and translating this into policy recommendations.

ENDOMIX strongly focuses on EDCs and their possible combined effects with other stressors, including socioeconomic aspects, and addresses an area that is under-researched and where knowledge is grossly lacking. Exposure to EDCs is associated with important adverse health outcomes in humans across the life course, including impaired respiratory and cardiometabolic health, neurodevelopment autoimmunity, and altered reproductive health⁹. These constitute health outcomes with a large burden of disease worldwide¹⁰. The exact underlying biological pathways are mostly unclear. Many studies overlook the fact that there are age windows in which exposure to EDCs are more critical, making certain populations like pregnant women, neonates, infants and children more vulnerable to their effects. ENDOMIX takes a unique approach to this problem by focusing on a) chemical mixtures (real life EDCs), b) immunotoxicity as a critical central mechanism, c) strong study designs, of multiple European cohorts with data on chemical exposures and NCDs across the life course, d) modelling approaches complemented by bioassays that provide novel knowledge about real-life mixtures and their effects, e) mechanistic and causal molecular investigation including *in vitro* barrier and target organ models as well as different animal species considering the 3R rules, and f) knowledge synthesis through novel text mining approaches for biomechanistic insights, modelling and risk estimation.

Existing gaps in scientific understanding, policy, and knowledge transfer hamper the effectiveness of European regulations in assessing, preventing, and reducing human and environmental

exposure to EDCs. Addressing this uncertainty by integrating robust data sources, existing data from biobank samples, modelling strategies, and bioassays will be **transformative in identifying real-life mixtures that are of concern and should be looked at more carefully**. The effects of chemical mixtures may be more significant than their components, potentially causing irreversible adverse effects during vulnerable periods of life such as pregnancy, early childhood, and adolescence. This aligns with the Developmental Origins of Health and Disease (DOHaD) framework, which posits that many adult diseases originate in early life, with chemical exposure during these vulnerable periods potentially driving adverse health outcomes^{7,11}. Adolescence is a key period of rapid and unique development, in which individuals may be very prone to major endocrine and metabolic changes, and thus potentially highly sensitive to EDCs, but this has rarely been examined in epidemiological studies. Further, it is not considered in the design of single *in vivo* studies nor experimental settings for risk assessment. ENDOMIX will therefore break new ground by focussing on puberty endpoints.

A recent report of the Lancet Commission for Planetary Health identified **immunotoxicity**, the focus of **ENDOMIX**, as one of “three particularly worrisome, and inadequately charted consequences of chemical pollution”¹², the other two being neurotoxicity and reproductive toxicity. Even though that it is documented that acute or chronic EDC exposure on the immune system results in autoimmune diseases¹³, or common diseases like diabetes, obesity, allergies and respiratory diseases, the impact of EDCs on health outcomes mediated by the immune system is poorly acknowledged or completely overlooked in most of current approaches. ENDOMIX will advance the field by studying immunotoxicity as a driver of deviations in human health development following exposure to EDCs, and a perpetuator of pathologies.

Dysregulated immune pathways are known drivers of common diseases such as diabetes, obesity and respiratory diseases. In particular, dysregulated immune responses in pregnancy may have long-term effects on offspring, even if the pregnancy seemed normal. The fact that EDCs can affect immune responses upon binding to the hormone receptors expressed on the surface of or in immune cells^{14,15} and cause abnormalities relevant to pathology is poorly recognized or not recognized at all. The primary focus of ENDOMIX on the emerging field of immunotoxicity is not limited to immune-related diseases, but applies to a wide range of pathophysiological conditions. Acute or chronic exposure to EDC chemicals and mixtures can impact the immunome, a term used to comprise the genes and proteins that constitute the immune system¹⁶, and also affect the frequency, phenotype and functionality of immune cells, with different effects depending on individual predisposition, time and duration of exposure. However, whether and how exposure to chemicals, and in particular EDCs and chemical mixtures of concern, is associated with immune-mediated pathologies has not been studied in depth. The vision of ENDOMIX is to fully elucidate and understand the overall effects of complex EDC mixtures and the underlying mechanisms.

In ENDOMIX, we employ a tiered approach to investigate the effects of chemicals and their mixtures across models of increasing physiological complexity, ranging from cell-based systems to *in vivo* models. The first tier comprises high-throughput assays designed to measure molecular initiating events and key biological responses, such as the quantitative activation of nuclear receptors and transcription factors in reporter gene assays (e.g., estrogen receptor, NF- κ B, thyroid receptors). The second tier involves more advanced methods that go beyond single endpoints by employing primary immune cells (PBMCs) obtained from donor blood samples. We have already established flow cytometry protocols to assess the impact of chemicals on multiple immune cell subsets¹⁷. Within ENDOMIX, we will further refine these methodologies to characterize how chemical mixtures influence immune cell subsets, functional parameters such as cytokine secretion, and activation status. This approach also allows us to identify immune cell subpopulations warranting more detailed investigation. Subsequently, we are developing specific assays for selected immune cell types to gain a deeper mechanistic understanding of chemical effects at the single-cell level.

To address the complexity of linking *in vitro* findings and health outcomes, ENDOMIX employs an innovative triangulation strategy that integrates evidence from cohort studies, *in vitro*, and *in vivo* models focusing on the same chemical mixtures. This multi-layered approach is designed to move beyond associative findings and towards the identification of causal immune targets of EDCs (Figure 1). In a first step candidate EDC mixtures relevant for endocrine disruption, immunotoxicity and immunomodulation will be identified using a previously developed prioritization workflow for neurotoxic chemicals based on simulated worst case exposure, high-throughput toxicokinetics models and high-throughput toxicity data with data-gap filling through toxicity prediction models¹⁸. The identified potential mixture effect contributors will be searched for in population-based blood exposure data from a large collection of 16 cohorts and cohort consortia European cohorts including target and non-target analysis using high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) data. Based on this information, complex EDC mixtures will be reconstituted in the laboratory at the concentration ratios as they were detected in human blood. The reconstituted mixtures will be used to investigate their effects at the level of immune cells and target organs. The concentration ratios of the chemicals in the mixtures correspond to the concentrations found in the cohort samples, but the overall concentration is higher to be able to measure but the results will be extrapolated down to the real-life concentrations. Tissue barrier systems, organ-on-a-chip-approaches and zebrafish embryo models behavioral assays will be utilized to understand EDCs' impact on defined endpoints. By combining the gained knowledge on defined associations between exposures and health outcomes and identified cell- and organ-dependent mechanisms, we will continue using cohort samples and model systems to understand causality between these exposures and defined health outcomes and identify underlying mechanisms. Finally, at the end of the project, we will be able to provide evidence-based recommendations to regulators

Figure 1. The ENDOMIX strategy from data generation to its translation into policy guidelines and recommendations. With a combination of life-course population-based cohort data, high-throughput screening and modelling to identify new mixtures of concern, *in vitro* cell, barrier and organoid models, *in vivo* models, omics, and computational approaches, ENDOMIX will deliver evidence-based guidelines and advice to citizens on improving human health.

and policy makers, inform the public and contribute to improved risk assessment.

ENDOMIX objectives

ENDOMIX aims at unravel the overall immunotoxic or immunomodulatory impact of EDC mixtures leading to adverse health outcomes. **The overarching objective of ENDOMIX is to deliver new information and concepts about the immune-mediated health impact of EDC mixtures, and their underlying biological mechanisms, which will build the basis to elaborate on approaches that help minimize EDC exposures in the future.**

Mixtures identified as potentially concerning will be tested in *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays, including primary immune cells, organoids, alternative models such as *Caenorhabditis elegans* and zebrafish embryos, and classic mouse models to uncover mechanistic insights. Barrier models will be used to determine the transport and targets of EDC mixtures. Computational approaches will bolster associations between multiple exposures and health outcomes.

Our objective is to provide clear scientific evidence on exposure scenarios, co-exposures' effects (including lifestyle and

socioeconomic factors), target cells and organs, and mechanistic pathways. ENDOMIX will integrate harmonised data on EDC exposures, immune markers, and health outcome endpoints from multiple European cohorts to accelerate this integrative approach. Additionally, we will identify novel bioactive EDCs through predictive exposure and toxicokinetic modelling, combined with data mining from high-throughput screening (HTS) bioassays, with an emphasis on immunotoxicity and immunomodulation, to prioritise drivers of mixture effects.

Objective 1: Identification of complex EDC mixtures in European populations

Existing knowledge about EDC impact on health mostly came from studies of single chemicals and previous experimental design is often insufficient as they focus on known chemicals only. People are exposed to a wide range of EDCs that can potentially interact and will certainly act together in mixtures. Therefore, it is vital to improve our understanding of the effects of exposure to real-life EDC scenarios at different life stages. Additionally, the problem is that there are potentially thousands of chemicals in our blood and there are hundreds of chemicals that potentially cause endocrine disruption and immunomodulation, but they were never systematically matched to

identify chemicals that are mixture effect drivers. ENDOMIX cutting edge and novel approach is that we will simulate mixtures of potential concern by data mining of the toxicology literature, simulating mixture exposure with help of high-throughput toxicokinetic modelling and mixture effect models. This approach has so far led to >7000 candidate chemicals out of a starting list of 100,000 chemicals that could potentially be contributing to mixture effects. ENDOMIX will derive complex EDC mixtures and health outcomes in European populations using an exceptional wealth of data and biosamples analysis by systematic *in silico* prioritization leveraging toxicology literature, high-throughput toxicity & exposure methods and mixture effect models. *In silico* mixtures predictions will be augmented with existing blood biomonitoring data through searching for candidate chemicals of concern data from cohort samples within the consortium. Newly detected bioactive compounds will be confirmed in a small subset of blood samples from the cohorts before complex chemical mixtures are designed for testing in the HTS assays.

ENDOMIX will design *in vitro* studies to analyse endpoints that are relevant for immunotoxicants and associated mediators of health outcomes as defined in the cohort studies.

Based on key characteristics (KC) of immunotoxicity, we will select adequate HTS assays addressing relevant key events of endocrine disruption and immunomodulation as a comprehensive apical endpoint of immunotoxicity in innate and adaptive immune cells. These assays are suitable for screening large numbers of chemicals, mixtures and ultimately even extracts from blood samples of the cohorts. The large number of screened chemicals and mixtures in the HTS assays will then be used to develop a smaller number of representative mixtures of immunotoxicants that will be tested in more specialised and more complex bioassays, primary cell cultures and *in vivo* model systems.

Our strategy starts with population-based studies that include many cohorts covering the life course (prenatal, perinatal, infancy, childhood, adolescence, adulthood) and comprising regions across Europe and beyond with very detailed data (Participating cohorts, Figure 2). ENDOMIX not only brings together large multiple existing cohorts with already measured EDCs in biosamples, but its novelty lies in the identification and study of EDC as mixtures and the focus on the immune-mediated effects of EDCs. In addition to the identification of new mixture contributors, ENDOMIX will use existing targeted

Figure 2. Overview of the observational studies involved in ENDOMIX. Cohort study name, life course timepoints (pregnancy, infancy, childhood, adolescence, and adulthood) and illustration with coloured signs representing the availability of chemical exposure data measured with targeted analysis throughout the life course is shown. Further, available microbiome, epigenome, transcriptomics, and metabolomics data are indicated.

screening data of a number of EDCs: polychlorinated biphenyls, organochlorine pesticides, per- and polyfluorinated compounds, metals, parabens, phthalates, phenols, and organophosphate pesticides. Further, for cohorts with limited availability of EDC data, such as for relatively rare outcomes like autoimmune diseases, we will proceed to quantify chemicals suspected to contribute to immunotoxic mixture effects, such as polychlorinated biphenyls, organochlorine pesticides, and per- and polyfluorinated compounds. Another strength is the covering of various life stages allowing the study of different windows of susceptibility to EDCs including early-life and adolescence, two major sensitive periods subject to important endocrine and physiological changes. We expect that EDC mixtures may vary over time due to changes in EDC use, exposure sources, and policies, and across different populations depending on determinants such as age, sex, socioeconomic status, and lifestyle habits. In addition to most of the identification of new mixture contributors, involved cohorts benefit from exposure and health outcome data already harmonised in the context of previous or ongoing EU-funded projects including the LifeCycle project¹⁹ and projects that are part of the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN, including ATHLETE²⁰, LongITools²¹ and Expanse²²). ENDOMIX will use existing targeted screening data of a number of EDCs: polychlorinated biphenyls, organochlorine pesticides, per- and polyfluorinated compounds, metals, parabens, phthalates, phenols, and organophosphate pesticides.

Objective 2: Associations between exposure to EDC mixtures, occurrence of allergies and respiratory, cardiometabolic and reproductive health as well as autoimmunity

Mixtures that occur in real life will be tested for immunotoxic effects from HTS using *in vitro* bioassays and predictive exposure models. After identifying mixtures of concern and testing their effects in simple bioassays, we will examine their potential determinants including socioeconomic, environmental and lifestyle-related factors and their link with several important health outcomes, of which; the choice was based on the potential involvement of the immune system as a mediator of disease development. Immune cells can be targeted by EDCs, are ubiquitous in the human body, can traffic to target organs and if dysfunctional, they are able to initiate, trigger or perpetuate disease. Health outcomes to be studied within ENDOMIX therefore are (1) allergies & respiratory health (eczema, atopic dermatitis, allergic rhinitis, wheezing, asthma, lung function, COPD), (2) cardiometabolic & cardiovascular health (body mass index, waist circumference, adiposity, dyslipidemia, insulin resistance, diabetes, stroke, acute myocardial infarction) (3) reproductive health (age at menarche, age at voice break, Tanner stages, menstrual cycle characteristics, sex hormone levels), and (4) autoimmune diseases (rheumatoid arthritis, ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease). The health outcomes will be studied at different age periods, from childhood to adulthood (e.g., from early changes in blood pressure to the onset of cardiovascular diseases) in cohorts and disease models. We will additionally explore how EDCs may be associated with overall health by analysing their potential effects

on more than one health outcome, an approach particularly relevant for public health to identify the EDC mixtures that contribute to multimorbidity.

The association of EDCs with the health outcomes may be linked to central immunotoxicity processes with a focus on inflammation. ENDOMIX will identify immune markers focused on inflammation using a proteomics approach and will examine their relation with EDC exposure. Immune markers focused on inflammation will comprise cytokines, chemokines, their respective receptors and a wide range of other immune proteins that will be identified through novel proteomic analyses using Olink® inflammation panels. Many biological pathways, metabolic perturbations may serve as biological pathways involved in immune-related effects of EDCs on human health. ENDOMIX will make use of available epigenetic, microbiomic, and endogenous metabolomic data of participants of the human cohorts. By doing so, we will offer insights into the relationships of exposure to EDCs, immune markers and DNA methylation, microbiome, and metabolome at multiple life stages and their association with human health outcomes.

Studying EDC mixtures in epidemiology raises methodological challenges due to the high correlations between different EDCs and the high dimension of data to be considered (tens to hundreds of chemicals). ENDOMIX will overcome these challenges by using advanced statistical methods suitable for chemical mixtures. These include unsupervised dimensionality reduction and clustering methods that will allow the identification of specific profiles of exposure independently of their health effects, and supervised techniques (e.g., Bayesian Kernel Machine Regression, Quantile G-computation) to estimate both the overall effect of the EDC mixture on disease risk and the contribution of each individual compound to the mixture effect. Another statistical challenge is the integration of immunological markers as potential intermediate endpoints between EDC exposure and health. We will perform mediation analysis in a high dimensional context to disentangle the direct and indirect effect of EDCs through changes in immunological markers. To synthesize information across different biological layers, we will use a multi-omics framework using graphical networks and multi-block approaches, such as two-way orthogonal PLS (O2PLS) and multi-omics factor analysis (MOFA), to integrate the information from EDC exposures, omics layers, possible sex differences and disease outcome.

Objective 3: Impact of prioritized EDC mixtures on the immunome, innate and adaptive immune cell functionality and target organs

To investigate the direct effects of priority EDC mixtures on the immunome, innate and adaptive immune cells' frequency, phenotype and functionality, we will first characterise the immunome and which cell subtypes are the most affected by EDC mixtures by mass cytometry, based on CyTOF® (cytometry by time of flight) technology. The unique metal labelling of antibodies allows the simultaneous identification of up to 50 protein markers in one cell with the further advantage of no background signal compared to other methods. After

identifying the cell subtypes affected the most, more specific immunoassays involving innate and adaptive immune cell populations will be employed to test the impact of chemicals. Moreover, cytokine-bead arrays will be applied to determine cytokines in monocyte, dendritic cell, T and B cell culture supernatants to gain further insights into cytokine secretion patterns²³. For T cells, maturation and differentiation assays will be conducted under chemical treatment. For B cells, alterations in antibody production (Ab) capacity (e.g. IgG, IgM) will be determined under the impact of EDC mixtures. In some approaches, effects of EDC mixtures will be tested under parallel stimulation with bacterial and viral motifs, namely pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) and intracellular molecules associated with cellular damage, called damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs). Together, these assays will provide detailed information about EDC effects on immune cell differentiation, maturation, plasticity and functionality and will thus increase our knowledge on chemical drivers of acute and chronic diseases. Moreover, our findings will provide information on how EDCs may alter immune responses against pathogens²⁴⁻²⁶. Finally, gene expression analyses using semi-high-throughput qPCR and omics approaches will be employed in chemical-exposed immune cell populations to gain further insights in altered intracellular pathways.

Further, barrier and organ *in vitro* models including organoids will unravel how EDCs behave within tissues, and how EDC mixtures cross barriers and if immune cells work as messengers or mediators of organ toxicity. The models were carefully chosen to be meaningful regarding the health endpoints studied in cohorts. Besides using human *in vitro* models, as described above, we will employ innovative models that faithfully mimic the organs of interest and human response (Figure 3).

Here, barrier models, co-culture and 3D models, including organoids and organ-on-a-chip models that are already published and running in the laboratories of the ENDOMIX partners, will be used. When adequate or possible, immune cells will be combined with the cell systems. These systems include: *in vitro* lung barrier^{27,28}, *in vitro* blood-brain-barrier^{29,30}, *in vitro* placenta barrier³¹ and *in vitro* intestinal barrier^{32,33}.

Further, for target organ models, we use lung organoids³⁴, *in vitro* heart spheroids^{35,36}, intestinal organoids^{37,38} and liver spheroids^{39,40}. Immune cells will be co-cultured to understand EDC effect on their interaction. At the molecular level, we will identify gene and protein expressions of nutrient transporters, regulation of genes related to lipid and glucose metabolism gene and associated transcriptional factors, and perform nuclear receptor transactivation assays. Established gene and protein signatures indicative of triglyceride accumulation⁴¹ will be transferred to further models to derive characteristic and predictive gene expression patterns *in vitro*, indicative of a certain endocrine effect.

Organoids will be generated from primary samples, like placenta organoids or will be stem-cell derived. Multi-organ *in vitro* models will be used to study interactions between different organs (e.g. intestinal-hepatic interaction or liver-adipocyte interaction) and the effect on chemical biotransformation. Because of its defined short life cycle, *C. elegans* can be exploited to test the effect of chemicals on the whole life cycle of an organism (from egg production to development to mature organism). Our innate immune models with *C. elegans* include bacterial infection models and detection of antimicrobial proteins and peptides. EDC mixtures and individual chemicals will be tested on development and innate immune responses by *C. elegans*^{42,43}. Moreover, a zebrafish embryo model will be used to complement *in vitro* approaches as *C. elegans* to evaluate the impact of EDC on the outcome of metabolic liver diseases and on related intestine-liver axis disruptions including alterations of microbiota and immune cell functions. The zebrafish embryo model represents a 3R-compliant⁴⁴, alternative model that, up to 5 days post-fertilization (dpf), is considered to be a non-protected life stage, according to EU regulations⁴⁵.

There is a gap in the availability of complex, higher-throughput immunotoxicity screening systems. We propose that the zebrafish embryo model can fill this gap, particularly for identifying innate immunotoxicants, as the innate immune system develops in isolation in 5-day-old zebrafish embryos. A new alternative assay to detect innate system immunomodulation

Figure 3. Models used in ENDOMIX. Different models are used in ENDOMIX to study the impact of endocrine disrupting chemical (EDC) mixtures in tissue barriers, cell-cell interaction and whole organisms.

will be developed and applied in embryonic zebrafish that quantitates, in parallel, a concentration-response relationship on a diverse suite of ~25 immunomodulatory molecules including markers for phagocytes (neutrophils, monocytes, macrophages), inflammation-related serum proteins (complement, C-reactive protein), antimicrobial peptides (defensins), cell receptors that signal a defensive response (TLRs), cells that release inflammatory mediators (macrophages, mast cells, NK cells), and markers of physical barriers (tight junctions). In addition, automated morphometrics will be applied to quantitate gastrointestinal area which, when increased in the absence of other morphological effects, may indicate intestinal inflammation. Individual chemicals and mixtures developed in this project will be tested in a concentration response format. Transgenic lines labelling neutrophils or macrophages will be used to quantify immune cell migration into the gastrointestinal (GI) tract.

Critical periods of exposure and possible sex differences are also considered in ENDOMIX's design as for example placenta organoids and immune cells from both sexes are employed to represent exposure that affects not only mother and offspring in a transgenerational approach but also sex-related disease development. The use of alternative models including transgenic zebrafish with labelled macrophages and *C. elegans* as a model of dysbiosis will provide valuable data on EDC impact and immune-mediated mechanisms and thereby greatly reduce the use of vertebrate animal experiments.

Objective 4: Establishment of causality of EDC exposure on health outcomes

The direct causality between exposure to EDC mixtures and deviations from normal healthy development or disease outcomes needs to be confirmed to deliver evidence for improved chemical regulations. ENDOMIX will utilize the information obtained in Objectives 1–3 to design studies addressing causality of EDC exposures on health outcomes. The models will further consider the EDC association with health outcomes through their impact on immune cells and target organs. These approaches include deep characterisation in cohort samples using omics-based biomarkers and the effect and perinatal exposure using transgenerational *in vivo* models. Experimental mouse models will be used whenever *in vitro* or alternative models cannot answer the scientific question. Mixtures identified previously will be tested in well-defined transgenerational 3R-conform mouse models to verify adverse effects observed in human cohorts and in *in vitro* models. Control treatment will depend on the nature of the defined mixtures. These models may include: asthma in the offspring of exposed mothers, rheumatoid arthritis in offspring of exposed mothers and will include mechanistic studies^{46–48}. As for *reproductive health*, we will study potential EDC effects on the reproductive performance of female and male offspring of EDC-exposed dams (same exposure protocol as for the other disease models)^{49,50}. To assess puberty onset in female offspring, we will assess vaginal opening and oestrous cycle analyses, and as ovarian follicle maturation analyses^{51,52}. For male offspring, sperm analyses will provide insights into their fertility status⁵³.

Objective 5: Engagement with regulators and providing guidance on exposure to the European community

The European public needs access to well-founded information on the effects of complex mixtures of EDCs to avoid disinformation. Citizens need to be empowered to self-regulate and reduce their exposure to EDCs and mixtures of concern in everyday life to increase the number of healthy life years. ENDOMIX will provide guidance on exposure to EDCs and mixtures and information about potential adverse effects and lay the ground work for regulatory changes and preventive measures for citizens, regulators, and relevant stakeholders within the healthcare value chain. The circle will be closed by using the generated information to develop action plans and recommendations to address priority mixtures of concern that impact health and proposing a more harmonized battery of risk assessment with specific toxicological endpoints and well-defined biomarkers.

To combine information from experimental and epidemiological studies conducted in ENDOMIX and existing and future literature, we will adopt a Weight-of-Evidence (WoE) approach. These approaches are commonly used in authoritative risk assessment programs by organizations such as the WHO, EU, and US-EPA^{37,54}. In addition, we will utilize novel text mining methodologies to create knowledge graphs that capture the relevant complex biomechanistic insights. Specifically, we will employ the Integrated Network and Dynamical Reasoning Assembler (INDRA) Reach (Reading and Assembling Contextual and Holistic Mechanisms from Text) environment, which uses automated large-scale reading of scientific literature, natural language processing (NLP) approaches, and structured databases to collect and assemble mechanistic understanding of cellular processes and associated health effects³⁹. This approach has already been successfully applied for genotoxic compounds⁵⁵ and will be extended to EDCs in this study. Through INDRA, mechanistic information from multiple sources will be de-duplicated, standardized, and assembled into sets of statements with associated evidence levels. These Statements can then be used to construct executable rule-based models and a variety of network models, such as knowledge graphs⁵⁵. We aim to assess the concordance between the traditional WoE approach and generated Statements to provide an expert-led assessment of the validity of this novel computational approach to evidence synthesis⁵⁶.

Science to policy translation

The scientific insights and knowledge generated by ENDOMIX will be the basis for subsequent application in policy making and development of new regulations. The consortium aims to develop new hands-on research-based guidance and policy options and will provide policy makers and decision makers with new data and evidence-based information. To strengthen the science-policy interface and promote acceptance and uptake of the developed new knowledge base and guidelines, active stakeholder involvement and a thorough consultation process will be ensured through the set-up of a dedicated Stakeholder Board (SHB). The SHB involves members advocating for future policies, scientific advisors, and a citizen representative

who provide input early on in the process to ensure their perspectives are considered when developing policy recommendations. ENDOMIX will contribute to the EU's goal to ensure EU policy making is based on evidence, provide simple, clear and transparent recommendations and involve stakeholders along the knowledge chain in the development. Further, communication and dissemination activities including educational approaches will facilitate science-to-policy translation of the ENDOMIX findings and guidelines.

The strategy chosen for ENDOMIX to fulfill the objectives is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 4.

Within ENDOMIX, we bring together renowned experts in toxicology, clinical science, environmental immunology, social, environmental and molecular epidemiology, biology, statistics and data science, and risk assessment. Exposure to chemicals

can lead to different adverse effects in humans depending on sex, gender, and age. Population studies have shown different exposure patterns in men and women that show a risk factor for diseases such as those related to the immune, reproductive, and metabolic area. Population-based data from the cohorts will be separately analysed for females and males to understand the possible different impacts of different EDC mixtures depending on the sex and on life stages. As for experimental models, ENDOMIX will incorporate the sex difference dimension into the toolbox by using *in vivo* data from animals of both sexes where available for benchmarking the *in vitro* assays and by adapting methods and protocols using cell lines from males as well as from females (where available) as research has shown the relevance of including both sexes in experiments³⁶. Thus, sex differences in sensitivity, sex-specific variables of biomarkers and sex-specific cut-off values will be considered. From a scientific point of view, sex parameters are

Figure 4. The ENDOMIX concept and workflow. The ENDOMIX project is structured into well-coordinated work packages (WPs) fostering an interdisciplinary approach to understanding the true impact of endocrine disrupting chemical (EDCs) on human health. In addition to the WPs related to the desired research outputs, work dedicated to project coordination and management, clustering activities and ethics requirement is underlying this concept.

specifically considered in our work and attempts to include cell lines and 3D organoids originating from tissues originating from males and females will be made wherever possible. ENDOMIX has already designed organoid studies to contemplate sex differences between female and male, this is particularly relevant for placenta organoids, where the origin of the tissue is often overlooked. Models relying on available cell lines may be a limiting factor for some of the outcomes. Molecular markers are available to determine sex and can be used for retrospective analyses of sex differences. In the epidemiological studies, the models will be adjusted for sex or stratified by sex where applicable.

In conclusion, the ENDOMIX project aims to unravel the complexity of exposure to EDCs and their impact on human health. In particular, ENDOMIX aims at contributing to the understanding of immune-mediated health outcomes and providing comprehensive insights into the biological mechanisms linking EDC exposure to adverse health outcomes, by incorporating multi-omics data, including immunomics, epigenomics, transcriptomics, metagenomics, and metabolomics so to enhance our understanding of the molecular pathways affected by EDCs. By employing already existing cohorts covering different life phases, ENDOMIX can explore the effects of early life EDC exposure and its influence on long-term health trajectories. The knowledge generated by ENDOMIX will inform evidence-based policy-making aimed at reducing EDC exposure, mitigating associated health risks, raising public

awareness about the risks of EDC exposure and promoting health-promoting behaviours.

Disclaimer

The views expressed in this article are those of the author(s). Publication in Open Research Europe does not imply endorsement of the European Commission.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required for writing this project summary. The ENDOMIX project itself will be conducted on existing prospectively collected data from different European cohort studies. All participating cohorts have been approved by the relevant ethics boards and informed consent was obtained for all participants.

All research that involves human data is conducted under the rules and legislation in place, including the Declaration of Helsinki, the IHC guideline for Good Clinical Practice, as well as the ISO guidelines on good clinical practice ISO 14155:2020, the European Directive 2001/20/EC on Good Clinical Practice, and the EU General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679).

Data availability statement

No data are associated with this article

References

1. Armocida B, Monasta L, Sawyer S, *et al.*: **Burden of non-communicable diseases among adolescents aged 10–24 years in the EU, 1990–2019: a systematic analysis of the Global Burden of Diseases Study 2019.** *Lancet Child Adolesc Health.* 2022; **6**(6): 367–383.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
2. Hameed A, Farooq T, Shabbir S: **Role of pharmaceuticals as EDCs in metabolic disorders.** *Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals-induced Metabolic Disorders and Treatment Strategies.* 2021; 357–365.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
3. Bergman A, Heindel JJ, Kasten T, *et al.*: **The impact of endocrine disruption: a consensus statement on the state of the science.** *Environ Health Perspect.* 2013; **121**(4): A104–6.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
4. Martin O, Scholze M, Ermler S, *et al.*: **Ten years of research on synergisms and antagonisms in chemical mixtures: a systematic review and quantitative reappraisal of mixture studies.** *Environ Int.* 2021; **146**: 106206.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
5. Bansal A, Henao-Mejia J, Simmons RA: **Immune system: an emerging player in mediating effects of endocrine disruptors on metabolic health.** *Endocrinology.* 2018; **159**(1): 32–45.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
6. World Health Organization: **Global assessment of the state-of-the-science of endocrine disruptors.** International Program on Chemical Safety, 2002.
[Reference Source](#)
7. Bergman A, Heindel JJ, Jobling S, *et al.*: **State of the science of endocrine disrupting chemicals 2012.** World Health Organization, 2013.
[Reference Source](#)
8. Gore AC, Chappell VA, Fenton SE, *et al.*: **EDC-2: the Endocrine Society's second scientific statement on Endocrine-Disrupting Chemicals.** *Endocr Rev.* 2015; **36**(6): E1–E150.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
9. Meyer A, Sandler DP, Beane Freeman LE, *et al.*: **Pesticide exposure and risk of rheumatoid arthritis among licensed male pesticide applicators in the agricultural health study.** *Environ Health Perspect.* 2017; **125**(7): 077010.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
10. Kahn LG, Philippat C, Nakayama SF, *et al.*: **Endocrine-Disrupting Chemicals: implications for human health.** *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol.* 2020; **8**(8): 703–718.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
11. United Nations Environment Programme: **UNEP 2013 Annual Report.** 2014.
[Reference Source](#)
12. Fuller R, Landrigan PJ, Balakrishnan K, *et al.*: **Pollution and health: a progress update.** *Lancet Planet Health.* 2022; **6**(6): e535–e547.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
13. Popescu M, Feldman TB, Chitnis T: **Interplay between endocrine disruptors and immunity: implications for diseases of autoreactive etiology.** *Front Pharmacol.* 2021; **12**: 626107.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
14. Cunningham M, Gilkeson G: **Estrogen receptors in immunity and autoimmunity.** *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol.* 2011; **40**(1): 66–73.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
15. Buskiewicz IA, Huber SA, Fairweather D: **Chapter 4 - Sex hormone receptor expression in the immune system.** In: Gretchen NN, Megan MM, editors. *Sex Differences in Physiology.* Boston: Academic Press, 2016; 45–60.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
16. Biancotto A, McCoy JP: **Studying the human immunome: the complexity of Comprehensive Leukocyte Immunophenotyping.** *High-Dimensional Single Cell Analysis: Mass Cytometry, Multi-parametric Flow Cytometry and Bioinformatic Techniques.* 2014; **377**: 23–60.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
17. Pierzchalski A, Zenclussen AC, Herberth G: **A comprehensive battery of flow cytometric immunoassays for the *in vitro* testing of chemical effects in**

- human blood cells. *Front Immunol.* 2024; 14: 1327960.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
18. Braun G, Escher BI: Prioritization of mixtures of neurotoxic chemicals for biomonitoring using high-throughput toxicokinetics and mixture toxicity modeling. *Environ Int.* 2023; 171: 107680.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 19. Jaddoe VVV, Felix JF, Andersen AMN, et al.: The LifeCycle Project-EU Child Cohort Network: a federated analysis infrastructure and harmonized data of more than 250,000 children and parents. *Eur J Epidemiol.* 2020; 35(7): 709–724.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 20. Vrijheid M, Basagaña X, Gonzalez JR, et al.: Advancing Tools for Human Early Lifecourse Exposome Research and Translation (ATHLETE): project overview. *Environ Epidemiol.* 2021; 5(5): e166.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 21. Ronkainen J, Nedelec R, Atehortua A, et al.: LongITools: dynamic longitudinal exposome trajectories in cardiovascular and metabolic noncommunicable diseases. *Environ Epidemiol.* 2022; 6(1): e184.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 22. Vlaanderen J, De Hoogh K, Hoek G, et al.: Developing the building blocks to elucidate the impact of the urban exposome on cardiometabolic-pulmonary disease: the EU EXPANSE project. *Environ Epidemiol.* 2021; 5(4): e162.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 23. Fischer F, Ermer MR, Howanski J, et al.: Single and mixture effects of Bisphenol A and Benzophenone-3 on *in vitro* T helper cell differentiation. *Chem Biol Interact.* 2024; 395: 111011.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 24. Del Río-Araiza VH, Mendoza MS, Castro KEN, et al.: Bisphenol A, an endocrine-disruptor compound, that modulates the immune response to infections. *Front Biosci (Landmark Ed).* 2021; 26(2): 346–62.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 25. Ustyugova IV, Frost LL, Van Dyke K, et al.: 3,4-Dichloropropionaniline suppresses normal macrophage function. *Toxicol Sci.* 2007; 97(2): 364–74.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 26. Hermanowicz A, Nawarska Z, Borys D, et al.: The neutrophil function and infectious diseases in workers occupationally exposed to organochloride insecticides. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health.* 1982; 50(4): 329–40.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 27. Kovar L, Wien L, Selzer D, et al.: In Vitro-In Silico modeling of Caffeine and Diclofenac Permeation in static and fluidic systems with a 16HBE lung cell barrier. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel).* 2022; 15(2): 250.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 28. Kohl Y, Müller M, Fink M, et al.: Development and characterization of a 96-well exposure system for safety assessment of nanomaterials. *Small.* 2023; 19(23): e2207207.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 29. Danz K, Höcherl T, Wien SL, et al.: Experimental comparison of primary and hiPS-based *In Vitro* Blood-Brain Barrier models for pharmacological research. *Pharmaceutics.* 2022; 14(4): 737.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 30. Rohde F, Danz K, Jung N, et al.: Electrospun scaffolds as cell culture substrates for the cultivation of an *in vitro* blood-brain barrier model using human induced pluripotent stem cells. *Pharmaceutics.* 2022; 14(6): 1308.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 31. Stojanovska V, Arnold S, Bauer M, et al.: Characterization of three-dimensional trophoblast spheroids: an alternative model to study the physiological properties of the placental unit. *Cells.* 2022; 11(18): 2884.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 32. Stock V, Bohmert L, Coban G, et al.: Microplastics and nanoplastics: size, surface and dispersant - What causes the effect? *Toxicol In Vitro.* 2022; 80: 105314.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 33. Paul MB, Schlieff M, Daher H, et al.: A human Caco-2-based co-culture model of the inflamed intestinal mucosa for particle toxicity studies. *In vitro Models.* 2023; 2(1–2): 43–64.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 34. Mason RJ, Dobbs LG: Alveolar epithelium and pulmonary surfactant. *Murray and Nadel's Textbook of Respiratory Medicine.* 2016; 1: 134–149.e5.
[Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 35. Fischer B, Meier A, Dehne A, et al.: A complete workflow for the differentiation and the dissociation of hiPSC-derived cardiospheres. *Stem Cell Res.* 2018; 32: 65–72.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 36. Lauschke K, Rosenmai AK, Meiser I, et al.: A novel human pluripotent stem cell-based assay to predict developmental toxicity. *Arch Toxicol.* 2020; 94(11): 3831–46.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 37. Vandenberg LN, Agerstrand M, Beronius A, et al.: A proposed framework for the Systematic Review and Integrated Assessment (SYRINA) of endocrine disrupting chemicals. *Environ Health.* 2016; 15(1): 74.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 38. Klooster JPT, Bol-Schoenmakers M, van Summeren K, et al.: Enterocytes, fibroblasts and myeloid cells synergize in anti-bacterial and anti-viral pathways with IL22 as the central cytokine. *Commun Biol.* 2021; 4(1): 631.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 39. Bachman JA, Gyori BM, Sorger PK: Automated assembly of molecular mechanisms at scale from text mining and curated databases. *Mol Syst Biol.* 2023; 19(5): e11325.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 40. Rose S, Ezan F, Cuvellier M, et al.: Generation of proliferating human adult hepatocytes using optimized 3D culture conditions. *Sci Rep.* 2021; 11(1): 515.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 41. Lichtenstein D, Mentz A, Sprenger H, et al.: A targeted transcriptomics approach for the determination of mixture effects of pesticides. *Toxicology.* 2021; 460: 152892.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 42. Bhalla D, Steijaert MN, Poppelaars ES, et al.: DARTpaths, an *in silico* platform to investigate molecular mechanisms of compounds. *Bioinformatics.* 2023; 39(1): btac767.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 43. van der Voet M, Teunis M, Louter-van de Haar J, et al.: Towards a reporting guideline for developmental and reproductive toxicology testing in *C. elegans* and other nematodes. *Toxicol Res (Camb).* 2021; 10(6): 1202–10.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 44. Hubrecht RC, Carter E: The 3Rs and humane experimental technique: implementing change. *Animals (Basel).* 2019; 9(10): 754.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 45. Strähle U, Scholz S, Geisler R, et al.: Zebrafish embryos as an alternative to animal experiments—a commentary on the definition of the onset of protected life stages in animal welfare regulations. *Reprod Toxicol.* 2012; 33(2): 128–32.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 46. Buchenauer L, Haange SB, Bauer M, et al.: Maternal exposure of mice to glyphosate induces depression- and anxiety-like behavior in the offspring via alterations of the gut-brain axis. *Sci Total Environ.* 2023; 905: 167034.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 47. Buchenauer L, Junge KM, Haange SB, et al.: Glyphosate differentially affects the allergic immune response across generations in mice. *Sci Total Environ.* 2022; 850: 157973.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 48. Fischer F, Kretschmer T, Seifert P, et al.: Single and combined exposures to Bisphenol A and Benzophenone-3 during early mouse pregnancy have differential effects on fetal and placental development. *Sci Total Environ.* 2024; 922: 171386.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 49. Santamaria CG, Meyer N, Schumacher A, et al.: Dermal exposure to the UV filter Benzophenone-3 during early pregnancy affects fetal growth and sex ratio of the progeny in mice. *Arch Toxicol.* 2020; 94(8): 2847–2859.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
 50. Müller JE, Meyer N, Santamaria CG, et al.: Bisphenol A exposure during early pregnancy impairs uterine spiral artery remodeling and provokes intrauterine growth restriction in mice. *Sci Rep.* 2018; 8(1): 9196.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 51. Gaytan F, Morales C, Leon S, et al.: Development and validation of a method for precise dating of female puberty in laboratory rodents: the Puberty ovarian maturation Score (Pub-Score). *Sci Rep.* 2017; 7: 46381.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 52. Chen Y, Liu Q, Liu R, et al.: A prepubertal mice model to study the growth pattern of early ovarian follicles. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2021; 22(10): 5130.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 53. Jeschke L, Santamaria CG, Meyer N, et al.: Early-Pregnancy Dydrogesterone supplementation mimicking luteal-phase support in ART patients did not provoke major reproductive disorders in pregnant mice and their progeny. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2021; 22(10): 5403.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 54. Pipal M, Wiklund L, Caccia S, et al.: Assessment of Endocrine Disruptive properties of PFOS: EFSA/ECHA guidance case study utilising AOP networks and alternative methods. *EFSA J.* 2022; 20(Suppl 1): e200418.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 55. Scholten B, Simón LG, Krishnan S, et al.: Automated network assembly of mechanistic literature for informed evidence identification to support cancer risk assessment. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2022; 130(3): 37002.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
 56. Miller I, Diepenbroek C, Rijntjes E, et al.: Gender specific differences in the liver proteome of rats exposed to short term and low-concentration Hexabromocyclododecane (HBCD). *Toxicol Res (Camb).* 2016; 5(5): 1273–1283.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 29 August 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.20658.r55593>

© 2025 Köhrle J. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

? **Josef Köhrle**

¹ Charité-Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Berlin, Germany

² Charité-Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Berlin, Germany

Acute and chronic exposure to environmental chemicals, especially those targeting the endocrine and reproductive systems and crucial neurodevelopmental processes, has been demonstrated to be associated with predisposition, emergence and deterioration of common diseases, especially if exposure occurs during intrauterine development and sensitive developmental windows of the growing and maturing organism. Mechanistic evidence, clear cause-effect relationships between exposure and adverse outcome, established by using informative animal experimental models, and recently accumulating human epidemiological data provide strong support for adverse, frequently irreversible action of chemicals contained in our nutrition, drinking water, cosmetics and consumer products. Limited information is available so far for their adversity on the metabolic and immune system.

The authors provide a detailed outline of an EU funded project addressing the potential adverse impact of exposures to realistic mixtures of (environmental) chemicals targeting components of the immune system and related diseases. Currently, information on adverse effect of chemicals (not only EDCs) mainly is based on analyses of mechanisms and endpoints for single compound, while realistic exposure scenarios comprise complex mixtures and multiple routes of exposure. The ENDOMIX team intends a multimodal application and combination of several methodological approaches to identify biomarkers accessible by large cohort studies for various advisory policies.

As the immune system is involved in many crucial processes relevant for health and disease the planned studies might significantly contribute to clarify which chemical mixtures and which of their main components are associated with or even causally involved with adverse outcome of developmental or chronic impact of mixture exposures. Currently, it is still unclear whether underlying mechanisms result in immuno-, neuro-, repro- or endocrino-toxic effects or their combination. Obviously, statements (chapter ENDOMIX objectives) like *“The vision of ENDOMIX is to fully elucidate and understand the overall effects of complex EDC mixtures and the underlying mechanisms. Our strategy is to cover the entire knowledge chain to achieve this ambitious goal ...”*,

graphically summarized in Fig.1, are not only 'ambitious', but maybe considered as overambitious, boastful and probably unrealistic for the given time frame, team composition and budget restrictions and in the context of many research teams who worldwide work on this complex thematic with serious efforts!

It is also questionable whether the goal will be achieved that "*ENDOMIX will deliver **evidence-based guidelines and advice to citizens on improving human health***". Guidelines is a very clearly defined term in biomedicine. At its best, if successful, ENDOMIX might delineate some **guidance** information for individuals, risk groups, regulatory authorities or policy makers. But consolidation of such information will still need to be confirmed and validated by implementation of properly powered prospective (mid-/long-term) studies which might generate such clinically-relevant evidence for clinical practice and best patient care, including prevention of disease. Authors should be more cautious in their terminology and tone down expectations of the outcome of this challenging project.

The chosen conventional and innovative state of the art models (8!) for testing the selected mixtures are suitable for the intended purpose and probably will allow identification of novel EDCs and prioritization of drivers of adverse mixture effects with the focus on the immune system. Less clear remains the selection of the chemical mixtures to be tested in the various models based on the exposome data that will be collected from the various cohorts studied. Probably, the inclusion of some already established EDC reference mixtures (e.g. ovarian fluid, amniotic fluid along pregnancy trimesters) that have been studied in recent EU-funded projects would provide benchmarks and allow comparability with existing data. Whether ENDOMIX team will take advantage the extensive HBM4EU exposure information gathered during the last decade and exploit this data remains unclear.

ENDOMIX will have access to chemical exposure data from observational studies from several cohorts across Europe which cover various life phases from pregnancy to adulthood (Fig. 2) and will provide rather complex data (microbiome, epigenome, transcriptome and metabolome) on various chemicals contained in real-life mixtures in context of a broad spectrum of disease parameters. Nevertheless, the complexity of this data and the complexity of the immunotoxicity focus of this project will remain a tremendous challenge for its exploitation.

Whether the 5 main immune system-related health outcome goals of this project (Objective 2) can be achieved with the chosen strategy, selected models and method spectrum provided by the multidisciplinary but very heterogeneously composed team of experts remains to be seen.

The team also expects to fill the gap between in vitro model systems to the immune system operating in an intact organism (e.g. from stem cell-derived organoids to the intact organism across its life phases) by exploiting the *C. elegans* innate immune response and zebrafish embryo models. As mentioned before this seems more than ambitious in its extent of goals, parameters and endpoints to be analyzed. Couldn't they decide to leave something out and to prioritize and focus on some key aspects instead of presenting a panoptic scenario?

In objective 4 the ENDOMIX consortium intends to establish causality of EDC mixture exposure on health outcomes and realistically also plans to use experimental mouse models when the chosen in vitro approaches will reach their predictive and informative limits required for extrapolation and interpretation of in vivo conditions. However, they do not elaborate in detail for which diseases

which proper mouse models are existing and for which they are still lacking and where their limitations are in context of immunotoxic EDC effects and mechanisms involved.

The last and 5th objective focusses on future **guidance** for consumers and the society to avoid and reduce EDC exposure. Are there any strategies, benchmarks, criteria already available how potential endpoints of preventive measures can be established, validated and tested for their applicability and success?

This project will provide novel insight into the role of immunotoxic effects of EDC exposure during various life phases. It will contribute to a better understanding of the impact, role and interactions of the immune system for developmental processes relevant for the endocrine, reproduction and neurological systems. It can be expected that data accumulated by the EU-funded ENDOMIX consortium can contribute to better **guidance** for reduction of individual, environmental and societal EDC exposure which can only complement EU regulatory measures to stop the production, further distribution and application of identified and suspected endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs), which are substance of very high concern (SVHC) like mutagens, carcinogens and reprotoxicants. Probably, several of these chemicals and their mixtures not only act as EDCs but are also neurotoxic and/or immunotoxic, adversely impacting the health of living organisms including humans, especially during development in an irreversible manner.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Partly

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Yes

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: molecular aspects of the thyroid hormone system (biosynthesis, distribution, metabolism, action, regulation); effects of endocrine active compounds (endocrine disruptors) upon the thyroid hormone system; interaction between essential trace elements (iodine, selenium, iron) and the endocrine system; development of analytical methods for endocrine-relevant

ligands.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 22 July 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.20658.r55598>

© 2025 Robert J. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Jacques Robert

¹ University of Rochester Medical Center, Rochester, USA

² University of Rochester Medical Center, Rochester, USA

This is an interesting manuscript that presents the ENDOMIX project, which is an ambitious integrative approach to model and measure how real-life endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) act in mixtures to target the immune system and initiate, trigger or maintain disease. ENDOMIX is also anticipated to allow the identification of biomarkers and patterns of chemical exposures that would be convenient to measure, available for large cohorts and indicative for adverse health outcomes. The manuscript is mainly a description of the ENDOMIX approach and anticipated outcomes. As such, the plan is sufficiently detailed and convincing, although it would be great to see some real data to determine how successful this approach will be. The manuscript would benefit from a short preliminary set of real data using ENDOMIX. Overall, the manuscript is well written. There are a few points listed below that the authors may consider that would improve the manuscript.

1) It is unclear how robust the prediction of the potential additive or synergistic effects of different EDCs can be based on their structure. Some clarification would be helpful. In addition, the possibility of interaction between degradation products of the different EDCs as well as the possible interaction of EDCs and their degradation products with metabolites in human tissues should be considered. Some discussion of this complex issue and potential limitation of ENDOMIX would be welcomed.

2) An important immune function targeted by EDCs that is unfortunately completely omitted in this manuscript is the defects in immune responses to pathogens leading to increased susceptibility to infectious diseases such as influenza and other bacterial pathogens. There are multiple published data from mouse and the amphibian *Xenopus* models as well as epidemiologic data. Including EDC impacts on this key function of the immune system is crucial and would markedly strengthen the manuscript.

3) While zebrafish is mentioned as an alternative model, the *Xenopus* model is left out, which is unfortunate owing to its potential for assessing the direct impacts of EDCs on the development of

adaptive immunity as well as the indirect EDC effect on immune system development through the thyroid axis. In addition, the Amphibian Metamorphosis Assay (AMA) is a well-established test to determine if a given toxicant has potential to be a thyroid-disrupting chemical (TDC), and guidelines for the AMA have been endorsed by the US Environmental Protection Agency and Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). This makes *Xenopus* an important element in the regulation of industrial chemicals by government entities.

4) There is little discussion regarding the validation of the data obtained through ENDOMIX. For such a large approach a systematic validation system should be delineated.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Partly

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Yes

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Comparative immunology, immunotoxicology.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 14 Nov 2025

Thi Anh Mai Pham

Thank you for your valuable and constructive feedback on our manuscript. We have carefully considered the points raised and prepared a detailed, point-by-point response to each comment, indicating the corresponding changes made in the manuscript and where they can be found in the revised version:

This is an interesting manuscript that presents the ENDOMIX project, which is an ambitious integrative approach to model and measure how real-life endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) act in mixtures to target the immune system and initiate, trigger or maintain disease. ENDOMIX is also anticipated to allow the identification of biomarkers and patterns of chemical exposures that would be convenient to measure, available for large cohorts and indicative for adverse health outcomes. The manuscript is mainly a description of the ENDOMIX approach and anticipate outcomes. As such, the plan is sufficiently detailed and convincing, although it would be great to see some real data to determine how successful this approach will be. The manuscript would benefit from a short preliminary set of real data using ENDOMIX. Overall, the manuscript is well written. There are a few points listed below that the authors may consider that would improve the manuscript.

Author response: Thanks very much for this positive feedback. As for real data sets, we prefer at this stage to refrain of including data as this is not a classic manuscript but an open letter and this kind of format does not allow for primary data. Besides, given the complexity of a consortium project, it would be difficult to pick one data set to represent to whole consortium.

1) It is unclear how robust the prediction of the potential additive or synergistic effects of different EDCs can be based on their structure. Some clarification would be helpful. In addition, the possibility of interaction between degradation products of the different EDCs as well as the possible interaction of EDCs and their degradation products with metabolites in human tissues should be considered. Some discussion of this complex issue and potential limitation of ENDOMIX would be welcomed.

Author response: From a public health and regulatory perspective, the central question is whether an endocrine-disrupting chemical (EDC) can exert detrimental effects on human health—regardless of whether the toxicity originates from the parent compound or its degradation products/metabolites.

In epidemiological studies, the decision to measure either the parent compound or its metabolites is guided by the goal of accurately characterizing participants' exposure levels. For EDCs that are rapidly metabolized upon entering the human body (e.g., phthalates, organophosphate pesticides), exposure is typically assessed via the quantification of their metabolites. In contrast, for more persistent EDCs (e.g., organochlorines, PFAS), exposure is generally evaluated by measuring the parent compounds directly.

In whole-organism studies (both epidemiological and *in vivo*), the organism is exposed to the parent compound, which is subsequently metabolized by endogenous pathways. Consequently, the subject is effectively exposed to both the parent compound and its metabolites, and any observed toxicity may result from either or both forms. It is important to acknowledge, however, that humans may also be directly exposed to certain metabolites, and that interindividual variability in metabolic capacity can lead to exposure misclassification in population studies.

Greater concern arises in *in vitro* (and potentially *in silico*) systems, where the metabolic capacity of the test model may be limited or absent. In such cases, exposing cells solely to the parent compound could yield misleading results—particularly if the toxic effect is mediated by metabolites rather than the parent chemical. To address this limitation, it is advisable to test both the parent compound and relevant metabolites when feasible,

ensuring a more comprehensive assessment of potential toxic effects. However, our focus is on mixtures. In complex mixtures, the concentration-additive nature of effects becomes largely independent of chemical structure and synergistic effects less important. This additive hypothesis can be tested by comparing responses from single compounds with those from their mixtures—a strategy that has been shown to hold true within one order of magnitude in previous studies. In the ENDOMIX project, our goal is to analyze real-life mixtures. Therefore, as long as robust exposure data are available for both parent compounds and their transformation products, we will design mixtures that include both and systematically assess their effects.

2) An important immune function targeted by EDCs that is unfortunately completely omitted in this manuscript is the defects in immune responses to pathogens leading to increase susceptibility to infectious diseases such as influenza and other bacterial pathogens. There are multiple published data from mouse and the amphibian *Xenopus* models as well as epidemiologic data. Including EDC impacts on this key function of the immune system is crucial and would markedly strengthen the manuscript.

Author response: We agree with the reviewer that this is highly relevant topic and very much related to the immune system. While infectious were not the focus of the project, basically because the health outcomes of the included cohorts do not specifically deal with infectious diseases, we still have included some aspects in our design. For example, in some in vitro approaches, effects of EDC mixtures will be tested under parallel stimulation with bacterial and viral motifs, namely pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) and intracellular molecules associated with cellular damage, called damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs). Together, these assays will provide detailed information about EDC effects on immune cell differentiation, maturation, plasticity and functionality and will thus increase our knowledge on chemical drivers of acute and chronic diseases. Moreover, our findings will provide information on how EDCs may alter immune responses against pathogens. For clarification, we have revised the first paragraph under “Objective 3: Impact of prioritized EDC mixtures on the immunome, innate and adaptive immune cell functionality and target organs” providing the explanation mentioned and included three additional references (PMIDs: 33049673, 17355946, 7174118). We agree with the reviewer that the *Xenopus* model represents a strong system to investigate adaptive immunity and thyroid axis disruption. While the embryonic/larval zebrafish model is able to capture thyroid disrupting chemicals (PMID: 26765085), adaptive immunity can only be assessed in older fish, necessitating lower throughput testing that requires an approved animal use protocol. Here, we opted to complement mammalian testing with rapid, early life stage zebrafish-based screening to identify human-relevant chemicals and mixtures that trigger intestinal inflammation. Future work should consider using a *Xenopus* or juvenile-based zebrafish systems to study the effects of ENDOMIX mixtures on adaptive immunity development and function.

3) While zebrafish is mentioned as an alternative model, the *Xenopus* model is left out, which is unfortunate owing its potential for assessing the direct impacts of EDCs on the development of adaptive immunity as well as the indirect EDC effect on immune system development through the thyroid axis. In addition, the Amphibian Metamorphosis Assay (AMA) is a well-established test to determine if a given toxicant

has potential to be a thyroid-disrupting chemical (TDC), and guidelines for the AMA have been endorsed by the US Environmental Protection Agency and Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). This makes Xenopus an important element in the regulation of industrial chemicals by government entities.

Author response: We appreciate the reviewer's suggestion and acknowledge that Xenopus model offers advantages for thyroid hormone disruption-related investigations, nevertheless it is not a common model for studying human immunotoxicity, which is the primary focus of ENDOMIX project. In contrast, zebrafish have been widely adopted as a relevant and suitable model for immunotoxicity research, namely for targets within the innate immunity, as shown in recent literature (e.g. reviews by Zhao et al., 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.ecoenv.2024.116023; Franza et al., 2024, doi: 10.3390/ijms252212008). Moreover, the Amphibian Metamorphosis Assay (AMA) based on *Xenopus laevis* falls outside the general scope of our project, which focuses namely on the development and implementation of 3R (Replacement, Reduction, Refinement) -compliant approaches complemented by limited in vivo testing using specific mammalian models with direct relevance for human immune health. Unlike the involved in vitro methods and the Fish Embryo Toxicity (FET) assay, the AMA does not align with the 3Rs strategy due to its longer exposure duration of 21 days. Furthermore, AMA primarily focuses on metamorphosis as an endpoint, which is not directly relevant to human health outcomes. Therefore, we chose to include immune disruption-related endpoints in zebrafish embryos as a suitable model within the context of our study.

4) There is little discussion regarding the validation of the data obtained through ENDOMIX. For such a large approach a systematic validation system should be delineated.

Author response: As for internal data validation, we envision different levels. Firstly, data analytical validation of results, internally but also comparing cross-cohort results takes place. We further have experimental validation, for example, the assessment of certain mixtures not only in populations, but also in vitro (cell models, organ models) and animal studies.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 19 February 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.20658.r49291>

© 2025 Varticovski L. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The author(s) is/are employees of the US Government and therefore domestic copyright protection in USA does not apply to this work. The work may be protected under the copyright laws of other jurisdictions when used in those jurisdictions.

Lyuba Varticovski

1

National Institutes of Health, Maryland, USA

² National Institutes of Health, Maryland, USA

The ENDOMIX project addresses a critical gap in research regarding the impact of EDCs on human health, with a particular emphasis on the immune system—an area that has been insufficiently explored in prior studies. This work is essential for gaining a comprehensive understanding of the extent of EDCs' effects on all living organisms, including both human and animal health.

The main weaknesses of the present manuscript lie in the details of the design and execution of these studies. For instance, the authors claim that “ENDOMIX will design *in vitro* studies to analyse endpoints relevant for immunotoxicants and associated mediators of health outcomes, as defined in the cohort studies.” These are two major undertakings that will require significant time and research investment.

Firstly, there are no established *in vitro* methods for assessing the immune system effects of low-level EDCs typically found in the environment, which are usually present at nano and picomolar concentrations. The authors do not appear to consider the labour-intensive and costly techniques currently used in studies on mammals and other species. Existing methodologies should be adapted to study biologically active relevant EDC concentrations in living cells, such as tracking the nuclear translocation of activated hormonal receptors. These are performed by analysing the nuclear/cytoplasmic ratio as the direct biological effect (PMID: 32018941). While such studies are pertinent to the immune system, assessing the nuclear/cytoplasmic ratio may present challenges when applied to immune cells.

Further references to existing methodologies (PMID 34339825), along with the authors' commentary on their potential applications in immune system research, are necessary to support the continuation of the ENDOMIX studies.

Secondly, to our knowledge, no established methodologies currently exist for linking *in vitro* studies to the associated mediators of health outcomes. All previous information has been based on correlations rather than direct evidence. If the authors intend to propose a novel approach for identifying the direct effect of EDCs on the immune system, it would be a significant advancement and would require a thorough, detailed explanation.

References

1. Varticovski L, Stavreva DA, McGowan A, Raziuddin R, et al.: Endocrine disruptors of sex hormone activities. *Mol Cell Endocrinol*. 2022; **539**: 111415 [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
2. Jones RR, Stavreva DA, Weyer PJ, Varticovski L, et al.: Pilot study of global endocrine disrupting activity in Iowa public drinking water utilities using cell-based assays. *Sci Total Environ*. 2020; **714**: 136317 [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

No

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

No

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Endocrine disruptors, Hormonal actions

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 14 Nov 2025

Thi Anh Mai Pham

We appreciate the reviewers' valuable comments and suggestions on our manuscript and would like to thank you for classifying the project as relevant and timely. We have carefully considered the points raised and prepared a detailed, point-by-point response to each comment, indicating the corresponding changes made in the manuscript and where they can be found in the revised version:

The main weaknesses of the present manuscript lie in the details of the design and execution of these studies. For instance, the authors claim that "ENDOMIX will design in vitro studies to analyse endpoints relevant for immunotoxicants and associated mediators of health outcomes, as defined in the cohort studies." These are two major undertakings that will require significant time and research investment. Firstly, there are no established in vitro methods for assessing the immune system effects of low-level EDCs typically found in the environment, which are usually present at nano and picomolar concentrations. The authors do not appear to consider the labour-intensive and costly techniques currently used in studies on mammals and other species. Existing methodologies should be adapted to study biologically active relevant EDC concentrations in living cells, such as tracking the nuclear translocation of activated hormonal receptors. These are performed by analysing the nuclear/cytoplasmic ratio as the direct biological effect (PMID: 32018941). While such studies are pertinent to the immune system, assessing the nuclear/cytoplasmic ratio may present challenges when applied to immune cells. Further references to existing methodologies (PMID 34339825), along with the authors' commentary on their potential applications in immune system research, are necessary to support the continuation of the ENDOMIX

studies.

Author response: Thank you for this valuable comment. We acknowledge that the methodological options for assessing the impact of chemicals at real-life concentrations remain limited, and addressing this gap is precisely where the ENDOMIX project aims to make a difference. It is important to distinguish between screening methods that can evaluate multiple chemicals based on general endpoints with regulatory potential, and more sophisticated methods that provide a detailed mechanistic understanding of how chemicals affect the immune system.

In ENDOMIX, we employ a tiered approach to investigate the effects of chemicals and their mixtures across models of increasing physiological complexity, ranging from cell-based systems to in vivo models. The first tier comprises high-throughput assays designed to measure molecular initiating events and key biological responses, such as the quantitative activation of nuclear receptors and transcription factors in reporter gene assays (e.g., estrogen receptor, NF- κ B, thyroid receptors).

For the high-throughput systems, we test mixtures at concentration ratios corresponding to those detected in environmental samples, but at slightly higher absolute concentrations to ensure measurable effects. Provided that these effects fall within the linear range of the concentration–response curves and linearity at low doses has been established, it is then possible to extrapolate the results to environmentally relevant concentrations.

Regarding the papers mentioned by the reviewer, we would like to note that the high-throughput in vitro assays used in ENDOMIX follow similar principles to those described in the first cited paper, which in fact references our earlier work on the application of reporter gene assays for water quality assessment. The main difference is that their setup is not high-throughput, as it relies on 96-well plates. The review article cited is indeed an excellent summary of endocrine disruptors acting on sex hormone pathways and describes many of the assays typically used in this field. We have extensive experience with these types of assays and have carefully considered them in our design. However, since our focus in ENDOMIX is on immunomodulatory endpoints, which are novel in this context, we prioritized selecting and optimizing assays relevant to immune function.

The second tier involves more advanced methods that go beyond single endpoints by employing primary immune cells (PBMCs) obtained from donor blood samples. We have already established flow cytometry protocols to assess the impact of chemicals on multiple immune cell subsets (doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2023.1327960). Within ENDOMIX, we will further refine these methodologies to characterize how chemical mixtures influence immune cell subsets, functional parameters such as cytokine secretion, and activation status. This approach also allows us to identify immune cell subpopulations warranting more detailed investigation. Subsequently, we are developing specific assays for selected immune cell types to gain a deeper mechanistic understanding of chemical effects at the single-cell level. For clarification, we have added a new paragraph under the section “ENDOMIX conception” providing the explanation mentioned above.

Secondly, to our knowledge, no established methodologies currently exist for linking in vitro studies to the associated mediators of health outcomes. All previous information has been based on correlations rather than direct evidence. If the authors intend to propose a novel approach for identifying the direct effect of EDCs on the immune system, it would be a significant advancement and would require a thorough, detailed explanation.

Author response: We fully agree that establishing direct links between in vitro findings and health outcomes is inherently challenging. To address this complexity, ENDOMIX employs an innovative triangulation strategy that integrates evidence from cohort studies, in vitro, and in vivo models focusing on the same chemical mixtures. This multi-layered approach is designed to move beyond associative findings and towards the identification of causal immune targets of endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs).

In the cohort studies, chemical exposure data are linked to OLINK-derived proteomic profiles that capture subtle changes in immune parameters. This enables us to determine whether specific mixtures are associated with inflammatory signatures, immune suppression, or intracellular signaling alterations, and how these relate to defined health outcomes. By combining exposure data with molecular and clinical endpoints, we can generate biologically meaningful hypotheses that guide mechanistic testing.

In the in vitro component, the same mixtures are systematically tested in human immune cell models to dissect their effects on inflammatory pathways, cytokine secretion, and immune functionality across defined cell subtypes. These mechanistic data provide insight into the cellular and molecular processes underlying the associations observed in human populations.

In parallel, the in vivo studies allow us to assess whether the same mixtures can elicit or exacerbate specific health outcomes under controlled conditions, while concurrently evaluating their immunomodulatory effects. This offers a critical bridge between molecular mechanisms and organism-level responses.

By integrating and cross-validating findings across these complementary tiers, ENDOMIX will generate a coherent, causality-oriented framework that connects environmental exposure to immune dysregulation and disease risk. This triangulated design represents a key strength of the project, enhancing both the robustness and translational relevance of the results.

To address the reviewers' comment, we have revised the paragraph describing the triangulated design under the section "ENDOMIX conception" according to the explanation mentioned above.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.